

THE CONCEPT OF BUSINESS DISCOURSE

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ABSTRACT

This research work deals with the analyzing the concept of the notion of business discourse and discusses the definitions of the concept in the point of view of different researchers.

In order to comprehend the meaning of “business discourse”, firstly we should clarify the meaning “discourse” itself. The word “discourse” came from latin roots “currere” means “to run” and dis- means “away”. Thus, the termin “discourse” is translated as “running away” and defines the flow of interaction among people. The termin “discourse” is firstly used by social theorist Michel Foucault. In general, the termin “discourse” is used for Arguments, viewpoints, and assertions that are supported by definitions, theories, and claims that fall under the purview of a specific field and are presented as facts (or “truths”).¹

A number of researchers have given different definitions to the termin discourse. For instance, according to Hinkel and Fotos “Discourse in context may consist of only one or two words as in stop or no smoking. Alternatively, a piece of discourse can be hundreds of thousands of words in length, as some novels are. A typical piece of discourse is somewhere between these two extremes”.² Henry and Tator define “discourse” as “the way in which language is used socially to convey broad historical meanings” and justify their theory like this: “It is language identified by the social conditions of its use, by who is using it and under what conditions. Language can never be 'neutral' because it bridges our personal and social worlds”.³ According to Baker and Ellece, “Discourse can...be used to refer to particular contexts of language use, and in this sense, it becomes similar to concepts like genre or text type. For example, we can conceptualize political discourse (the sort of language used in political contexts) or media discourse (language used in the media).

¹ What is Discourse | IGI Global

<https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/creating-analytical-lens-understanding-digital/7859>

² Hinkel, Eli, and Sandra Fotos, editors. *New Perspectives on Grammar Teaching in Second Language Classrooms*. Lawrence Erlbaum, 2001

³ Henry, Frances, and Carol Tator. *Discourses of Domination: Racial Bias in the Canadian English-Language Press*. University of Toronto, 2002.

In addition, some writers have conceived of discourse as related to particular topics, such as an environmental discourse or colonial discourse...Such labels sometimes suggest a particular attitude towards a topic (e.g. people engaging in environmental discourse would generally be expected to be concerned with protecting the environment rather than wasting resources). Related to this, Foucault...defines discourse more ideologically as 'practices which systematically form the objects of which they speak'.⁴

As a collaborative activity involving the active participation of two or more people, discourse is influenced by both the context of the communication itself and the experiences and knowledge of the participants. Herbert Clark used the idea of common ground to explain the different agreements that happen in effective communication in his discourse studies:

"Discourse is more than a message between sender and receiver. In fact, sender and receiver are metaphors that obfuscate what is really going on in communication. Specific illocutions have to be linked to the message depending on the situation in which discourse takes place...Clark compares language in use with a business transaction, paddling together in a canoe, playing cards or performing music in an orchestra.

A central notion in Clark's study is common ground. The joint activity is undertaken to accumulate the common ground of the participants. With common ground is meant the sum of the joint and mutual knowledge, beliefs and suppositions of the participants".⁵

The word "discourse" is used frequently and has multiple meanings across a wide range of academic fields, including critical theory, sociology, linguistics, philosophy, social psychology, and others. While business discourse is a type of institutional discourse, it is also a genre that is constrained by the social realm, specifically politics. Intentional, real, virtual, contextual, and psychological plans are all present, along with a variety of other functions that are both common and unique to business discourse. Schweitzer A.D. gives a comprehensive analysis of business discourse and reduces the existing linguistic approaches to its study to three main types:

- descriptive (rhetorical analysis of politicians' language behavior),
- critical (revealing social inequality expressed in discourse) and
- cognitive (analysis of frames and concepts of business discourse).⁶

The neat approach to the definition of discourse is noted in Nazarova T. B., he identifies eight meanings of the term "discourse" as:

1. an equivalent of the concept "speech", i.e. any particular saying;
2. a unit that is larger than a phrase,
3. the impact of the statement on his recipient in view of situations of utterance;
4. conversation as the main type of utterance;
5. speech from the perspective of the speaker as opposed to narration that does not take into account this position;
6. use of language units, their speech actualization;
7. socially or ideologically limited type sayings, for example, feminist discourse and etc.;
8. theoretical construct intended for research text production conditions. ⁷

⁴ Baker, Paul, and Sibonile Ellece. Key Terms in Discourse Analysis. 1st ed., Bloomsbury Academic, 2013.

⁵ Renkema, Jan. Introduction to Discourse Studies. John Benjamins, 2004.

⁶ Schweitzer A.D. Modern sociolinguistics. Theory. Problems. Methods.-M., 2006. p. 22-29

⁷ Nazarova T. B. The English language of business communication: a training course for students

Presnukhina I. A. identifies three main characteristics of discourse:

- 1) formal, this is a unit of language that exceeds the sentence in terms of content;
- 2) according to its content, discourse is related to language use in a social context;
- 3) according to its structure, the discourse is interactive, i.e. dialogic.⁸

Following the definitions of discourse offered by van Dijk⁹, Fairclough¹⁰, and Wodak and Chilton¹¹, we can define business discourse as the verbalization of business mentality, manifested in the form of a large number of texts on various business topics that are thematically related and taken into account in conjunction with their extra-linguistic contexts. The term "business discourse" has a broad definition and includes several "thematic subspecies," such as "economic discourse," "corporate discourse," and "negotiation discourse," among others.

The term 'discourse' has been defined as sets of statements that bring social objects into being.¹² In using the term 'organizational discourse', we refer to the structured collections of texts embodied in the practices of talking and writing (as well as a wide variety of visual representations and cultural artefacts) that bring organizationally related objects into being as these texts are produced, disseminated, and consumed.¹³

Compared to organizational discourse, the word "business discourse" refers to a wider range of social activity. (just as organisational discourse per se contains elements foreign to strategic action). Business discourse is a goal-oriented discourse that is concerned with conducting transactions that are economically advantageous, striking deals that favor one party over another, and ultimately—in one way or another—accumulating money. The "bottom line" is the term typically used to describe the latter goal. Business Discourse must create and maintain organizational structures and relationships that serve as a conduit for its actions in order to achieve this, though.

A "society of consumption" in the "age of information" has emerged in 21st-century society, marking a new step in its evolution. The former USSR republics, Eastern Europe, and the nations of the so-called "emerging economies"—China, India, and Brazil—have all seen a rise in market relationships and business philosophy (or "business mentality"). Business now plays a significant part in people's lives on a global scale and has sparked new social thought. It is one of the most potent forces driving social development. For its verbal and communication requirements, business has needed to use some applied discipline.

Since language is produced by thought and produces it, thereby creating and altering reality, the practical value of business linguistics relates to the mastery of language resources that can be achieved by professionals (and students) in business administration, management,

of philology - in English. language.) - M.: DialogMSU, 2000. p 37 - 38

⁸ Presnukhina I. A. Business communication in the light of diatopic variation of modern English. - M., 2005 p. 15

⁹ Van Dijk, T. A. (1993). Principles of critical discourse analysis. *Discourse & Society*, 4(2), 249-283

DISCOURSE = legitimation for certain attitudes, opinions etc.

¹⁰ Fairclough, N. (2012). Critical discourse analysis. *International Advances in Engineering and Technology*, 7, pp 452-487

"Discourses are diverse representations of social life." (p. 456)

¹¹ CDA is "about making connections between social and cultural structures and processes on the one hand, and properties of text on the other" Fairclough & Wodak, 1997, p. 277

¹² Parker, I. (1992). *Discourse Dynamics: Critical Analysis for Social and Individual Psychology*. London: Sage.

¹³ Phillips and Hardy 2002; Grant et al. 1998

economics, PR, advertising, and marketing. Business linguistics can improve specialists' and entrepreneurs' communication skills, aid in their comprehension of the nature of communication processes in their professional endeavors, and subsequently boost businesses' communication effectiveness.

The specifics of business language and interaction will help everyone understand the deeper inner meaning implied in socio-economic, corporate, and advertising discourse, as well as identify the manipulative mechanisms and techniques influencing public opinion (including those used by unfair business practices). On the contrary, we are all purchasers of products and amenities (produced and provided by business), and many people are also either beneficiaries or investors; as therefore, knowing the specifics of business language and communication.

A new perspective of "cross-border disciplines" is being stimulated by the recent accelerated info-technological development of society, which increases the interdisciplinary interaction of various areas of knowledge. In the sphere of language, business discourse is one these disciplines.

Business and business communication sublanguages each have unique characteristics that call for linguistic investigation. Numerous scholars have observed that business text differs from other types of text, such as scientific, publicist, fictional, and so on., in particular ways. The interactive, pragmatic, lexical, syntactic, textual, composite, visual-graphic, and other characteristics of business speech are evident. These justifications appear to be adequate to include "Business Linguistics" as a distinct field of study within the realm of Applied Linguistics.

Thus, Business Linguistics is a field that explores the specific functioning of language in a business context, investigates the use of language resources in business activities, and studies verbal and para-verbal aspects of business communication. The spectrum of its interests is based on a multidisciplinary synergetic approach and includes the following key areas:

- Business discourse, organizational, corporate and managerial communication;
- Oral, written and technically mediated communication in business, its typology and genre classification;
- Professional sublanguages of business sectors (e.g. those of banking, trading, accounting, manufacturing, administration, etc.);

Language of advertising and marketing, public relations (PR), the special language techniques for sales and marketing (including methods of psycho-verbal manipulation and neuro-linguistic programming);

- Lingua-pragmatics in a business context and Business Rhetoric (including specifics of a leader's speech, argumentative and persuasive communicative strategies for carrying out presentations, conducting meetings and negotiations, as well as the application of language resources in motivating, problemsolving, brainstorming, teambuilding, selecting personnel and its appraisal, (in)formality and (in)directness of business speech, formulating and conveying the meaning, building trust and rapport, and getting the feedback;

- Documentation (Document) linguistics: business correspondence and drafting contracts;

- Instructional (teaching) and academic language of business, economics and

management, used in textbooks and research, academic publications, lectures, case studies and training, consulting and coaching on business topics;

- Business lexicography (systematizing business terminology and composing thesauri of business vocabulary);
- Language of the business media;
- Intercultural business communication (including teaching / learning foreign languages for business purposes, as well as language in the workplace in multinationals, and language assessment).¹⁴

E.I. Sheigal distinguishes the following types of business discourse:

1. Institutional business discourse, in which only texts directly created by politicians and used in political communication (parliamentary transcripts, political documents, public speeches and interviews of political leaders, etc.) are used.

2. Mass business business discourse, in the framework of which uses texts created by journalists and distributed through the press, television, radio, the Internet.

3. Official-business business discourse related to hardware communication, in which the texts are created, intended for employees of the state apparatus.

4. Texts created by "ordinary citizens" who, not being professional politicians or journalists, occasionally participate in political communication. These can be various letters and appeals addressed to politicians or state institutions, letters to the business, etc.

5. "Political detectives", "political poetry" and texts very common in recent years, political memoirs.

6. Politics-dedicated texts of scientific communication.¹⁵

Business linguistics should focus on theories and useful techniques for teaching and learning "foreign languages for business purposes," particularly Business English, which serves as the de facto international business language in light of the geo-economic globalization that is occurring.

The subject of Business Linguistics is the study of language functioning in business and the linguistic component of business communication. The methodology of this new discipline should involve traditional research methods of discourse and of text as its result, discourse analysis, conversation analysis, empirical-descriptive and comparative techniques, cognitive, pragmatic and genre-style analysis, etc. The terminology and the scientific apparatus of Business Linguistics are still under construction, but they obviously could be built on the basis of those of the above- mentioned sister disciplines.

All types of linguistic data can be used as material for research – real or experimental, authentic or simulated data, as well as their combinations¹⁶

Business linguistics has been studied by many eminent academics and experts. (although, not using the term yet). In alphabetical order, F. Bargiela-Chiappini, L. Beamer, V. Bhatia, Ch. Candlin, A. Johns, C. Nickerson, A. Pennycook, G. Poncini, L. Putnam, C. Roberts, P. Rogers, H. Spencer-Oatey, J. Swales, I. Varner, L. Yeung, and others have made notable contributions to the study of business language and communication. By the 1990s' end, Ehlich and Wagner, Firth, Bargiela-Chiappini and Harris, Bargiela-Chiappini and Nickerson, and

¹⁴ Business linguistics and business discourse. Yulia V. Danuishina. Calidoscopio p. 241-242

¹⁵ Semiotics of political discourse. Sheigal E. I. (2004) p. 22-29

¹⁶ Business linguistics and business discourse. Yulia V. Danuishina. Calidoscopio p.242

others had established the topic of the research and the methodology for it. A gap "between contextual business approach and linguistic textual approach" was filled by tracing the relationship between the language and the business context.¹⁷

According to our opinion, research into how language functions in business should be founded on a discursive strategy, which denotes a significant level of speech penetration in daily life. The goal and focus of business linguistics research should be business conversation. The occurrence of discourse in general is multidimensional and polysemantic. Johns¹⁸ makes one of the earliest references to business discourse; she was also one of the first to use the phrase "the language of business" in academic work¹⁹. What does business talk actually mean? As "social action in business contexts," Bargiela-Chiappini defines it as "all about how people communicate using talk or writing in commercial organizations to get their work done."²⁰

Business discourse from the point of view has numerous functions. However, the most successful classification of functions in our opinion is applied by Yu.Akhmanova O.S.²¹:

1. The function of social control is regulative (the creation of prerequisites for the unification of behavior, thoughts, feelings and desires of a large number of individuals, that is, the manipulation of public consciousness).

2. The function of legitimizing power (explaining and justifying decisions regarding the distribution of power and public resources).

3. The function of the reproduction of power (strengthening the commitment to the system, in particular, through the ritual use of symbols).

4. Orientations (through the formulation of goals and problems, the formation of a picture of political reality in the mind of society).

5. The function of social solidarity (integration within the framework of the whole society or separate social groups).

6. The function of social differentiation (alienation of social groups).

7. Agonal function (initiation and resolution of social conflict, expression of disagreement and protest against the actions of the authorities).

8. Action function (implementation of policy through mobilization of the population: mobilization consists in activating and organizing supporters, whereas narcotization means the process of appeasement and distraction of attention, putting down vigilance)

References:

1. Baker Paul and Sibonile Ellece. Key Terms in Discourse Analysis. 1st ed. Bloomsbury Academic 2013.
2. Bargiela-Chiappini F.; NICKERSON C.; PLANKEN B. 2007. Business Discourse. Basingstoke Palgrave Macmil-lan 3 p.
3. Charles M. 1996. Business negotiations: Interdependence between discourse and the business relationship. English for Specific Purposes 15(1):19-36

¹⁷ CHARLES, M. 1996. Business negotiations: Interdependence between discourse and the business relationship. English for Specific Purposes, 15(1):19-36

¹⁸ JOHNS, A. 1980. Cohesion in written business discourse: Some contrasts. The ESP Journal, 1(1):35-44

¹⁹ JOHNS, A. 1986. The Language of Business. Annual Review of Applied Linguistics, 7:3-17

²⁰ BARGIELA-CHIAPPINI, F.; NICKERSON, C.; PLANKEN, B. 2007. Business Discourse. Basingstoke, Palgrave, Macmil-lan, 3 p.

²¹ Yu.Akhmanova O.S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. M., 2009. -507-521pp.

4. Fairclough N. (2012). Critical discourse analysis. *International Advances in Engineering and Technology* 7pp 452-487
5. Henry Frances and Carol Tator. *Discourses of Domination: Racial Bias in the Canadian English-Language Press*. University of Toronto 2002.
6. Hinkel Eli and Sandra Fotos editors. *New Perspectives on Grammar Teaching in Second Language Classrooms*. Lawrence Erlbaum 2001
7. Johns A. 1980. Cohesion in written business discourse: Some contrasts. *The ESP Journal* 1(1):35-44
8. Johns A. 1986. *The Language of Business*. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics* 7:3-17
9. Parker I. (1992). *Discourse Dynamics: Critical Analysis for Social and Individual Psychology*. London: Sage.
10. Yu.Akhmanova O.S. *Dictionary of linguistic terms*. M. 2009. -507-521pp.

